

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ACMEOLOGICAL POSITION OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the issue of developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment as a scientific and pedagogical problem. The study theoretically elucidates the essence of the acmeological approach, its role in the pedagogical system, and its influence on the professional and creative development of students in the context of digital transformation. The article also provides a scientific analysis of factors such as the formation of future teachers' digital competencies, self-awareness, the development of reflective activity, and the attainment of professional maturity. The research results make it possible to identify effective mechanisms for developing an acmeological position in a digital educational environment and to design pedagogical conditions that ensure personal and professional growth during the process of pedagogical practice.*

Keywords: *acmeology, digital education, acmeological position, acmeological knowledge, motivational-value, cognitive, communicative, emotional-volitional, reflective, organizational-activity components, impulsive level, formal level, optimal level, average indicator, efficiency, professional training, and others.*

Introduction.

In educational and scientific research institutions around the world, the transformation of the education sector and the preparation of competitive specialists for society require expanding modern technological knowledge, developing distance education based on digital technologies, virtual laboratories, and mobile technologies, as well as improving open educational resources and “blended learning” technologies. On an international scale, the development of science and technology, advanced industrial practices, and the rapid integration of changes occurring in society and nature demand the improvement of mechanisms for developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers within the digital educational environment. In this context, implementing intensive training, ensuring the integration of pedagogical and acmeological tasks in education, and developing acmeological orientation methods in professional training activities are of great importance. Such an approach to improving the educational environment based on acmeological knowledge necessitates special attention to scientific research focused on forming the acme-personality of a specialist and enhancing their professional readiness.

The experience of developed countries shows that the success of any advanced nation is closely linked to the ability of educators to elevate their creative activities to the highest “peaks.” One of the most important sciences that transforms the nature of teachers and influences the formation of their personality is pedagogical acmeology. It has been determined that one of the most powerful factors affecting the formation of an individual’s personality is the process through which the experiences accumulated by a person are transmitted to children through education. It is well known that the human personality is a complex psychological phenomenon that gradually

develops under the influence of specific factors throughout an individual's life. In this process, acmeology serves as a specialized science that studies human development and the process of achieving excellence.

As acmeology studies social phenomena within society, it explores how individuals, across different periods and circumstances, strive to create a stable life, overcome existing difficulties, express themselves through creativity, and pursue and attain goodness. In this sense, acmeology is a science that reveals the internal mechanisms of such activities and reflects the complex and challenging path of human choice aimed at achieving personal goals and self-fulfillment.

The purpose of the study: to develop scientific and methodological recommendations for the development of the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment.

The objectives of the study:

- To determine the structure and content of the development of the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment;
- To specify the tools, forms, methods, and opportunities for developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment;
- To design a model for the development of the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment;
- To identify the indicators and evaluate the effectiveness of developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment.

Research methods:

In the course of the study, the following methods were used: comparative study and critical analysis of scientific sources related to the problem, didactic materials, state educational standards, curricula and syllabi, educational and normative documents, textbooks, and instructional-methodological literature; interviews, observations, surveys, and testing; pedagogical experimentation; psychological-acmeological diagnostics; and mathematical-statistical analysis of the research results.

Research object:

The object of the study is the process of developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment. A total of 492 students specializing in primary education from Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Gulistan State University, and Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute were selected for participation in the research. The subject of the research is defined as the process of developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment. A total of 492 students from Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Gulistan State University, and Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute participated in the study.

The process of experimental work on developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment was carried out in several stages, each of which held particular significance. The diagnostic stage laid the foundation for the experimental study. During this phase, the essence of the activities implemented in higher education institutions and their legal and regulatory frameworks were thoroughly examined. In addition, pedagogical methods aimed at developing social relations among students were designed, and ways to enhance the effectiveness of this process were considered. In organizing the experimental work, it was essential to determine the level of development of the components that reflect the content of the acmeological position. For this purpose, we used questionnaires, tests,

and psychological-pedagogical methods to identify the state of development of such components as motivational-value, cognitive, communicative, emotional-volitional, reflective, and organizational-activity elements.

In order to determine the level of acmeological position in the experimental groups, interviews were organized to assess the level of acmeological knowledge and skills of future teachers. The interviews were conducted based on observations of students' activities. These interviews were carried out in an analytical and exploratory manner with the students, and particular attention was paid to the following conditions when designing the question-and-answer process:

1. the questions should be based on information that the participating students are familiar with;
2. the questions should not require answers limited to mechanical reproduction of previously learned material;
3. attention should be paid to ensuring the logical interconnection between the contents of the questions.

Thus, the analysis and research conducted during the diagnostic stage provided the initial data necessary for thoroughly planning and effectively implementing the subsequent stages. This phase determined the directions for developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers and identified the pedagogical actions required in this process, thereby creating a solid foundation for the following stages of the experimental work.

In analyzing the problem of developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment, six structurally meaningful components of conflictological competence were identified. These components include: motivational-value component, cognitive component, communicative component, emotional-volitional component, reflective component, and organizational-activity component.

In order to determine the level of development of the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital educational environment, it was concluded that it is first necessary to identify the criteria and levels of this development. It was explained that when defining these levels, it is important to take into account the motivational-value, cognitive, communicative, emotional-volitional, reflective, and organizational-activity criteria and indicators.

To assess the extent to which the structural components representing the content of the acmeological position are developed, a system of competence-based components was developed, including the motivational-value, cognitive, communicative, emotional-volitional, reflective, and organizational-activity criteria. Based on these, three levels of acmeological position development were identified: impulsive (low), formal (medium), and optimal (high).

Table 1

Indicators Reflecting the Current State of the Acmeological Position of Future Primary School Teachers in a Digital Educational Environment

HEIs		GULDU	BUXPI	TDPU	overall
Number of Students	Experimental group	60	86	106	252
	Control group	56	82	102	240
	In numbers	9	13	21	43

Experimental groups	Optimal (high)	In percent	15%	15.11%	19.81%	17.06%
	Formal (medium)	In numbers	26	37	43	96
		In percent	43.33%	43.02%	40.56%	38.09
	Impulsive (low)	In numbers	25	36	42	103
In percent		41.66%	48.83%	39.62%	40.87%	
Control groups	Optimal (high)	In numbers	8	11	15	34
		In percent	14.28%	13.41%	14.70%	14.16%
	Formal (medium)	In numbers	23	34	43	100
		In percent	41.07	41.46%	42.15%	41.66%
	Impulsive (low)	In numbers	25	37	44	106
		In percent	44.64%	45.12%	43.13%	44.16%

Results.

In the experimental groups, based on the established pedagogical conditions (intensive influence on the process of developing the acmeological position through reflexive-pedagogical methods; formation of acmeological knowledge among future primary school teachers; introduction of an acmeological terminology glossary; mastery of moderation and effective communication techniques), the process of developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers was carried out using reflexive-pedagogical methods.

Table 2

Final Results on the Development of the Acmeological Position of Future Primary School Teachers in a Digital Educational Environment

Criteria	HEIs	Experimental groups	Control groups	Experimental groups			Control groups		
				High	Medium	low	High	Medium	low
Motivational Value	Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami	106	102	21	52	33	10	19	73
	Gulistan State University	60	56	14	32	14	7	14	35
	Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute	86	82	17	41	28	8	15	59
	Overall	252	240	52	125	75	25	48	167
Cognitive	Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami	106	102	22	48	36	10	21	71
	Gulistan State University	60	56	15	32	13	7	15	34
	Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute	86	82	18	42	26	9	18	55
	Overall	252	240	55	122	75	26	54	160
Communicative	Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami	106	102	22	49	35	10	21	71
	Gulistan State University	60	56	16	31	13	8	14	34
	Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute	86	82	18	42	26	9	17	56
	Overall	252	240	56	122	74	27	52	161
Emotional-volitional	Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami	106	102	22	50	34	11	23	68
	Gulistan State University	60	56	16	31	13	8	15	33
	Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute	86	82	18	41	27	9	18	55
	Overall	252	240	56	122	74	28	56	156
Reflective	Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami	106	102	23	47	36	11	22	69
	Gulistan State University	60	56	16	30	14	8	14	34
	Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute	86	82	19	40	27	10	18	54
	Overall	252	240	58	117	77	29	54	157
Organizational-activity	Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami	106	102	22	48	36	11	19	72
	Gulistan State University	60	56	15	31	14	8	13	35
	Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute	86	82	18	41	27	9	16	57
	Overall	252	240	55	120	77	28	48	164

Figure 1

Average academic performance indicators of the experimental and control groups in developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers in a digital learning

Figure 2

Effectiveness indicators of the experimental and control groups in a digital educational environment

From the results, it can be observed that the outcomes of the selected experimental groups differ from those of the control groups at the end of the experiment. The average academic performance indicators demonstrate that the reflexive-pedagogical methods applied in the process of developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers, as well as the effectiveness of the structural-functional model and pedagogical conditions for fostering the acmeological position, are significantly higher in the experimental groups. Specifically, the effectiveness indicators increased by 1.15 times according to the motivational-value criterion, by 1.14 times according to the cognitive criterion, by 1.14 times according to the communicative criterion, by 1.13 times according to the emotional-volitional criterion, by 1.13 times according to the reflexive criterion, and by 1.14 times according to the organizational-activity criterion.

The fact that the confidence intervals do not overlap, along with the indicator of teaching effectiveness being greater than one and the indicator of learners' cognitive development being

greater than zero, provides statistical evidence — through mathematical methods — confirming the reliability and accuracy of the conducted research.

Discussion.

The structure for developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers is determined based on the stability of the interaction level and the dynamics of feedback among the motivational-value, cognitive, communicative, emotional-volitional, reflective, and organizational-activity components. The potential of pedagogical-psychological sciences in developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers is explained on the basis of internal integration among educational modules.

The model for developing the acmeological position of future primary school teachers was improved by taking into account the direct interrelation of such principles as integrity, continuity, consciousness and activity, differentiation and individuality, the unity of theory and practice, and reflective management, along with practically oriented functions, including initiative-based, cognitive-awareness, regulatory, communicative, prognostic, and managerial functions. Through the use of reflective methods, the effectiveness of pedagogical approaches aimed at intensively influencing the process of developing the acmeological position—by means of reflexive-pedagogical techniques and forming acmeological knowledge in future primary school teachers—was determined.

The relationship between the levels of development of the acmeological position in future primary school teachers and their behavioral strategies was identified. At the impulsive level of acmeological development, future primary school teachers tend to choose behavioral strategies based on their emotional state. At the formal level of development, they attempt to use several behavioral strategies, primarily relying on competitiveness and avoidance. At the optimal level of acmeological development, however, future primary school teachers are capable of flexibly applying all behavioral strategies — competitiveness, cooperation, compromise, avoidance, and adaptation — depending on the situation.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the research, the effectiveness of the improved functional-structural model for developing the acmeological position of future teachers through reflective methods — consisting of motivational-value, content, activity, and result-evaluation blocks — as well as the effectiveness of the proposed pedagogical conditions, was confirmed.

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